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Energy Efficiency and Buildings Thermal Comfort Indoor Adaptation Techniques Towards Resilient Buildings Operations in Nigeria: A Review

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ABSTRACT

This state-of-the-art literature study is being conducted against the backdrop of the knowledge gap in achieving resilient buildings. It is achievable within the context of design and construction to make buildings mitigate climate change effects due to their ability to integrate energy-efficient solutions. While the world is gradually transitioning to effectively using cleaner and better sources of energy like renewable energy, buildings that consume more energy must be more energy resilient and smarter towards withstanding associated crises and catastrophes that they are most often subjected to. The qualitative research involves a desktop review of peer reviewed articles downloaded from five data bases such as Scopus, Science Direct, Researchgate, Google Scholar and Web of Science were thoroughly searched using keywords such as resilience, thermal comfort, energy efficiency, occupant comfort and future weather were consulted during the period 2014-2024 where there was a systematic analysis of concepts and current trends. After thorough search, N=47 papers were selected for review from which inferences were drawn. The study revealed that it is however important to note that due to the adverse effects of unpredictable climatic trends that have arisen recently, considering resilient building design and performance at the initial and most flexible stages of a building's design becomes a very important consideration in the long run. Additionally, there are various mitigating and adoption strategies that aid enhancement of energy efficiency in building, improve thermal comfort and well-being of building occupants and also improving reductions in energy consumption. Due to the chosen research methodology, findings might not be generalizable and it is advised that further research should be conducted on the subject by adopting other research methodologies. The implications of the paper are that it would be beneficial to construction stakeholders, government policy makers, academia, building materials supplies and the business communities towards enhancing the development of the built environment further in Nigeria. The paper contributes to knowledge from this carefully researched work will be beneficial to stakeholders like academics, policy-makers, public health authorities and the business communities seeking to improve buildings' energy performances regarding resilience and adaptation strategies against climate change.

Keywords: Buildings, Climatic, Hazards, Knowledge, Mitigate, Resilient, Systematic.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Advanced weather predictions have the desired ability to assess building resilience concerning climate change and mitigation strategies towards achieving a balance between a building's comfort levels and its ability to withstand the harshness of Mother Nature (Ashrafiyan 2023). The author believes that these are necessary for achieving energy efficiency in buildings, comfort, sustainable infrastructures and necessary cost savings regarding energy consumption. Building resilience otherwise referred to in latin as *resillio* (Borghero, Clèries, Pean, Ortiz and Salom 2023) which means to bounce back refers to that ability of a building to absorb, plan and recover from an adverse weather condition imposed on it as frequently as these events occur (Hong, Malik, Krelling, O'Brien, Sun, Lamberts and Wei 2023). While there exists challenges that are related to the energy efficiency endeavor, the greatest challenge in enhancing sustainability is improving the well-being and health of everyone (Zhao, Aziz, Deng, Ujang and Xiao 2024). Nigeria experiences a varied degree of three adverse weather conditions which include the sahelian hot and semi-arid weather conditions of the North, the tropical monsoon climate that exists in the south and the tropical savannah climate for most of the central region (Patel and Chaudhary 2024). This according to the authors means that Nigeria has to balance the factors that determine the management of the carbon footprint in its built environment and also enhance the building occupants' thermal well-being and comfort conditions. Buildings are the ones that face these adverse structural and infrastructural defects regularly and also act as defensive shields against these climatic hazards (Stamatopoulos, Forouli, Stoian, Kouloukakis, Sarmas and Marinakis 2024). There is a knowledge gap of achieving resilient buildings which has resulted in the body of knowledge finding solutions and mitigating ideas that would address this very alarming trend (Rehman, Hamdy and Hasan 2024). As a result of research work on the subject of resilience, it has been identified that there are various types of building resilience techniques which are varied and not limited to fire, structural, thermal and often seismic resilience. It is however important to note that due to the adverse effects of unpredictable climatic trends that have arisen recently, considering resilient building design and performance at the initial and most flexible stages of a building's design becomes a very important consideration in the long run (Chen, Samuelson, Zou, Zheng and Cao 2023). Surveys of increased temperatures of buildings in certain locations have reported overheating and it is also expected to rise in other locations (Fernandez, Coutinho and Rodrigues 2024). The study further suggests ways to reduce high energy consumption and improve internal comfort for occupants such as proper ventilation strategies, and applications of renewable energy. Others include dedicated HVAC systems and cooling and this is what they believe is the set point standard in understanding whether the current office buildings would be ready to face future climate changes thereby improving comfort within them. Thermal resilience, on the other hand, has direct effects on building occupants' comfort and well-being. Due to increases in summer temperatures associated with climate change, the thermal resilience of actual buildings might not translate into effective indoor cooling of interior spaces thereby making them uncomfortable for building occupants (Borghero *et al* 2023). These heat waves have a huge impact on health and well-being thereby reducing the expected quality of life of building occupants (Borghero *et al* 2023).

Thermal comfort in office buildings is crucial in achieving increased office human workers' productivity levels. In addition thermal comfort conditions are also influenced by the surrounding climate, the built environment and the location the office building is domiciled (Lamsal, Bajracharya, and Rijal 2023). Since office buildings require air-conditioning systems to maintain a comfortable balance within them, these have the potential for energy savings and having an uncomfortable environment within them decreases workers' productivity (Kini, Garg and Kamath 2016). This awareness has highlighted the importance of providing standards relating to comfort that will assist designers in designing office spaces with tolerable indoor comfortable environments that will enable office building occupants to perform their respective desired tasks while also improving the building's energy performances regarding resilience and adaptation strategies against climate change (Liyanage, Hewage, Hussaini and Razi 2024). Stakeholders interested in thermal comfort resilience in buildings have been identified as engineers and architects, real estate developers, building owners, building occupants, commercial tenants, property managers and facility managers. Other stakeholder interests are utility providers and insurance property

companies. Fundamentally addressing issues of energy efficiency and thermal comfort in office buildings consistently highlights the gaps in the literature on future weather patterns and their effects on these building types in Nigeria. This study understands the importance placed on buildings since they have the unique characteristics of assembling different occupants within the building spaces who spend most of their productive lives indoors and enhancing thermal comfort within is key (Ashrafian 2023). This study aims to understand the effects of climate change on thermal comfort in buildings in Nigeria as well as adaptation strategies against climate change on building structures that enhance and create indoor environments that prioritizes occupant's well-being. In addressing the aim of the study, the research will be conducted based on objective reasoning which are associated with the studies main aim and focus which are determining the impact of adverse weather conditions on buildings in the varying Climatic spaces of Nigeria and their effects on thermal comfort in buildings. In addition, discussing the varying mitigation strategies adopted as resilient measures by building design in these climatic spaces and finally assessing the future trends in making buildings more energy efficient and resilient to climate change in the different climatic spaces within Nigeria.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

In arriving at the current literature regarding the studies area of focus, the research embarked on a two stage process that included: the procedure that was used for the literature search and the process for embarking on an inclusion and exclusion of relevant literature for the study. The study embarked on literature search from five scientific research repositories which included Scopus, Science Direct, Researchgate, Google Scholar and Web of Science. These were thoroughly searched using keywords such as resilience, thermal comfort, energy efficiency, office buildings, occupants comfort and future weather were consulted. The search strategies and the process for identifying relevant articles were implemented by inserting keywords, abstracts and titles of articles written from the period 2014-2024 into the search repositories of the relevant outlets selected for the study. The process of the review identified 85 papers to engage in a systematic review related to the topic of the study. This period of research interval was chosen due to the current challenges being faced worldwide as a result of climate change and secondly because considering more current literature would contain more innovative strategies associated with users comfort, adaptation strategies and challenges faced in ensuring energy efficiency in building spaces. These data bases were selected based on their broad research background containing various research articles related to the area of study in the scientific world and cover different scientific fields. A comprehensive screening of literature was carried out and at the end of the screening, an analysis of the selected texts were carried out since the articles were accessible in the respective data bases. Each of the research abstracts were carefully read to determine whether they could answer the studies area of focus and a portfolio was formed and an analysis was conducted to determine which of the articles would best suit the literature review process and documentation.

3.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Buildings have been developed within different built environments due to the local skills and materials available within a particular locality over time while also taking into consideration the different building forms and building orientations necessary to enhancing indoor occupants comfort (Saifudeen and Mani 2024). While these have helped in shaping the cityscape and local environments, buildings and infrastructure have been known to be affected by different climatic conditions. This has made it necessary to study adaptation strategies that are required in making them respond to these varying climatic conditions. Therefore, adaptation refers to the ability of a system to respond to changes and the effects caused by these changes (Saifudeen *et al* 2024). Therefore, it is expected that as a system responds to changes, its ability to respond to stress becomes inherent. One very important consideration in adaptation strategies is to incorporate adaptation measures from the onset of building projects and anticipated future projects development. Nigeria has evolved several climate change adaptation strategies which (Okeke 2024) suggests have arisen out of recent happenings regarding the effects of adverse weather conditions in the built environment. Such well thought out adaptation strategies include the National Adaptation

Framework plan, Strategic and Action plan on climate change, climate change act and the medium term national development plan. These have had their limitations due to a lack of follow up by successive administrations about continuous implementation and as such they have not been able to achieve the desired aim of improving adaptation of infrastructure due to the effects of climate change in the Nigerian built environment.

Climate change and its effects have greatly affected the Nigerian built environment compared to other parts of the world that have consistently tried to find ways of mitigating its effects on their regions (Tajudeen and Rodriguez 2024). The authors of this study have suggested that one of the climate change adaptation strategies that would have effective consequences on the built environment relates to proper zoning of building designs and emphasising proper zoning considerations in the design and construction of buildings (Tajudeen *et al* 2024). As a result, it is conclusive from their observations that when these climatic zoning considerations are effectively applied, understanding the correlation between different climatic conditions and rates of energy consumption can be the solution to building climate-responsive dwelling, offices and other building types. The use of energy in the built environment can be subdivided into various interrelated levels ranging from the associated materials used in the construction of buildings. Other uses include the design of the building from project inception to project completion, the rate of occupancy of the building, the ratings and efficiency of the appliances used in the building and finally the occupants of the building and how they behave within them (Opoku, Mensah and Ahadzie 2022).

It has often been suggested that active and passive design strategies offer effective solutions to achieving indoor thermal comfort of building occupants but as the global and local climates continue to change drastically, this assertion becomes very difficult to achieve (Choudry and Patel 2024). Passive design strategies like building orientation, natural ventilation, thermal mass, building insulation, shading, natural lighting, high performance windows and cool roofs need further reassessments in order to achieve maximum thermal comfort and energy efficiency. On the other hand also, active design strategies like HVAC systems, radiant heating and cooling, mechanical ventilation, heat recovery systems, building zoning, renewable energy and smart building automation also need adjustments (Choudry *et al* 2024).

3.1 Adaptation of Buildings to Climate Change in Nigeria

Anthropogenic factors otherwise referred to as human-triggered factors have been associated with climate change in recent times whereby buildings and the built environment have been major contributors to carbon emissions which have continued to distort the balance in global climate and indeed in Nigeria (Saricioğlu and Ayçam 2024). It is believed that the adaptation comfort climate concept of buildings emerged in the 1970s during the oil crisis that saw the need for nations to stop focusing on fossil-based fuels due to the environmental impacts associated with their uses Saifudeen and Mani 2024). While this was the first step in identifying the need for adaptation of buildings to climate change, various researchers have since identified the four characteristics of a building's adaptation as physical, adaptation characteristics, occupant, functional and natural environmental characteristics. These set of researchers think that each of these are complimentary to each other since thermal comfort within buildings would be an important determinant for building occupants that are familiar with the air-conditioned environment that they reside in. Other scholars have also suggested that there are currently three building design adaptation strategies in the Nigerian built environment (Adenaike and Olagunju 2024). These are structural adaptation, behavioral adaptation and resiliency. While structural adaptation refers to the ability of a structure to retain its safety factor after an adverse disturbance, behavioral adaptation refers to aspects of human behavior that assist in managing extreme weather conditions. These aspects of resilient adaptation deals with the capacity to foresee and make accommodations for and develop adaptive strategies when affected by severe threats.

Two major advantages that Nigeria has in adapting to climate change are enabled by the abundance of green vegetation in the built environment that have been referred to as green entrepreneurial opportunities and also having an abundance of renewable energy in the form of solar energy, wind and biomass (Oboti, Anabaraonye and Orji 2023). In addition to further ensuring that buildings adapt to the vagaries of climate change, other studies suggest climate-responsive designs as adaptation strategies (Lamsal, Bajracharya and Rijal 2021). Thus, in ensuring that cooling temperatures of office buildings are reduced,

using climatic elements like rainfall, humidity, wind and air temperature controls all aim at achieving users' thermal comfort within such building structures. It has also been decided that for Nigeria to enhance adherence to climate change goals which will mean an improved adaptation strategy for the built environment, some major deliverables would provide lasting solutions (Nwokolo, Meyer and Ahia 2024). These include adhering to theoretical pathways for Nigeria namely focusing on renewable energy generation, maximizing energy efficiency, providing huge investments in green infrastructure projects and placing maximum emphasis on investments that place more emphasis in the production of cleaner energy.

3.2 Energy Efficiency and Buildings Thermal Comfort Indoor Occupants Adaptation Techniques

In managing buildings, it has been observed that there is a double dilemma of bridging the gap between thermal comfort and energy efficiency which has always represented a challenge in complementing the two variables (Barbadilla-Martín, Martín, Lissen, Ramos and Domínguez 2018). As a way of achieving human centered and sustainable built environments, empirical studies have highlighted the importance of improving thermal comfort within buildings which is one of the objectives of sustainable development and thereby crafting spaces that allow for occupants comfort and well-being (Rane, Choudhary and Rane 2023). Associated with this is the need for effective energy consumption, energy efficiency and thermal comfort in buildings and suggestions have been made that various design variables can impact this three pronged scenario of consumption, efficiency and comfort (Lachir and Noufid 2024). It has recently been observed that thermal comfort in the built environment is a very complex subject that needs adequate attention due to differences in the physiological and psychological composition of each individual (Arowoia, Onososen, Moehler and Fang 2024). Thermal comfort in addition has been described as being more important than other aspects of the comfort of building occupants. Thermal comfort within building spaces has been described as one of the most fundamental deliverables in the design and construction of buildings whereby the occupants are satisfied with the thermal environment they are in and neither feel too hot nor too cold (Faraji, Rashidi, Rezaei and Rahnamayezekavat 2023). In addition, the authors agree that many of the disadvantages of having a bad thermal environment include being a potential health hazard which affects people's working abilities and office satisfaction with being at work.

Other scholars in addressing thermal comfort suggested that there are two models directly associated with knowledge relating to thermal comfort which are the heat balance theory and the adaptive model. The adaptive model refers to the ability of building occupants to adapt to noticeable thermal changes inherent within the environment domiciled while also enhancing comfortability (Arsad, Hod, Baharom and Jaafar 2024). Fundamental issues surrounding determining thermal comfort in buildings have been very complex to understand because thermal comfort is diverse as it is associated with age, gender, cultural background and the activity levels of occupants (Zhao, Aziz, Deng, Ujang and Xiao 2024). These have affected the applications of a one size fit all solution in addressing this subject. Such remedies like introducing adaptive comfort models which allow for occupant control of settings within buildings have been known to work.

Regarding energy efficiency solutions within buildings, (Zhao *et al* 2024) believe that buildings designed with energy efficiency strategies like the use of advanced glazing systems, enhanced insulation and using energy efficient HVAC systems are positive steps. Another study by (Khadka, Rijal, Amano, Saito, Imagawa, Uno, Genjo, Takata, Tsuzuki, Nakaya, Nishina, Hasegawa and Mori 2024) have referred to a hybrid building as being one of the best ways of ensuring occupants thermal comfort and energy efficiency strategies. These they have referred to as buildings that use a mixed mode system whereby in its space conditioning, it applies both natural ventilation and mechanical ventilation systems thereby encouraging behavioral adaptations to thermal comfort. Other studies on adopting smart buildings as climate change mitigation strategies (Ale 2024) have indicated that smart buildings help in maintaining energy efficiency in buildings and also have positive impacts on climate change impacts on the long run. Due to the peculiar weather conditions in Nigeria relating to high temperature levels and intense sunlight as a result of its tropical climate, studies by (Lekjep, Kagai, Chong and Baji 2024) suggest that using locally sustainable building materials like bamboo, wood, straw bales, Clay bricks and timber offer opportunities for energy efficiency in buildings and thermal controls within.

3.3 Building Retrofitting and Energy Efficiency in Buildings in Nigeria

Retrofitting existing buildings towards making them more energy efficient and increases their values while also enhancing their environmental impacts on the built environment (Iwuanyanwu, Gil-Ozoudeh, Okwandu and Ike 2024). The scholars believe that retrofitting existing buildings have varied advantages which include processes that upgrade and modify such buildings. This enhances the buildings energy efficiency, sustainability potentials while also improving their overall comfort in terms of thermal comfort and indoor environmental quality control. Retrofitting existing buildings can substantially reduce the carbon emissions of existing buildings and further helps to reduce the effects of climate change on the built environment. Again, (Ejidike, Mewomo and Olawumi 2022) in their study on global trends in retrofitting buildings by using smart technologies, suggests that retrofitting an existing structure can improve its thermal comfort and enhance their occupants well-being. In another study by (Ejidike, Mewomo, Agbajor and Olawumi 2023) on drivers for retrofitting, suggest that retrofitting existing buildings not only increases the buildings performance in terms of energy consumption but also improving the cost of operation of the building. It is further believed that energy consumption is predicted to rise in existing buildings in Nigeria due to rapid urbanization and retrofitting buildings is one of the surest ways to mitigate against the effects of the buildings on the built environment (Ejidike *et al* 2023). Cladding of buildings on the other hand offers the walls of buildings a lot of advantages in terms of energy consumption and climate change mitigating strategies. Using polyurethane boards as external cladding materials of selected buildings in Abuja by (Alegbe and Hammed 2024) offers savings in energy, comfort and energy efficiency in buildings. In another study on educational buildings in Lagos, (Ezema, Izobo-Martins and Owoseni 2022), the scholars suggest that there are possibilities of retrofitting school buildings with solar panels due to their immense foot prints but building heights but these are opportunities that have not been utilized.

One of the strategies used in retrofitting buildings within the built environment is the use of very good quality materials that result in low thermal resistance within and good indoor thermal comfort achieved for building occupants (Obi-George, Ifebi, Nwokorie, Maduka, Ibe, Okoro, Iweha 2024). It is also important to note that retrofitting existing buildings is quite a very comprehensive undertaking if energy efficiency and building occupants thermal comfort needS to be achieved. In their study on assessing the cost implications on adoption of energy efficiency strategies in hotel buildings in Lagos, (Salami, Taiwo, Ibem and Ajayi 2024), observed that a comprehensive LED lighting retrofit system were used (Plate 1), smart thermostats (Plate 2) and occupancy sensors (Plate 3) were upgraded in the guest rooms. Other retrofits strategies applied were the use of high efficiency window treatments (Plate 4), and the installation of slow flow shower heads (Plate 5) and faucets (Plate 6) in bathrooms.

Plate 1: Retrofit LED lighting system
Source: (Cheng *et al* 2024)

Plate 2: Smart Thermostats
Source: (Abdelmawla 2019)

Plate 3: *Occupancy Sensors*
Source: (Cheng et al 2024)

Plate 4: *High Efficiency Window Treatments*
Source: *Office of Energy Efficiency & Renewable Energy*

Plate 5: *Low Flow Shower Heads*
Source: (Tomberg 2024)

Plate 6: *Slow Flow Faucets*
Source: (Tomberg 2024)

In addition, smart water leak detection (Plate 7) for timely repairs and the use of high efficiency washers and dryers (Plate 8) have been a successful practice. Finally, high building envelopes in terms of double glazing (Plate 9) and high emissivity coating (Plate 10) also enhance thermal comfort in buildings.

Plate 7: *Smart Water Leak Detectors*
Source: (Yussof and Ho 2022)

Plate 8: *High Efficiency Washers and Dryers*
Source: (Cranston, Askalany and Santori 2019)

Plate 9: Building Envelopes In Terms Of Double Glazing
Source: (Tafakkori and Fattahi 2021)

Plate 10: High Emmissivity Windows
Source: (Kim, Park, Jang and Kim 2023)

3.4 How to Achieve Climate Resilient, Energy Efficient Buildings and Indoor Thermal Comfort in Nigeria

Climate change has become a global threat and as a result, it has become expedient to find ways of reducing the damaging effects of buildings on the built environment. One of such techniques as suggested by some scholars (Raimi and Lukman 2023) is the applications and awareness of climate friendly technologies while building. This view has been supported by (Akinola, Opoko, Ibem, Okagbue and Afolabi 2020) who discovered that the three major mitigation and adaptation strategies against the effects of climate change were planting of trees, greening and the use of energy efficient technologies. On the other hand, in another study by (Akomolafe, Clarke, Ayambire 2024), the scholars agree that in Nigeria, building energy efficiency use has become one of the innovative measures currently embarked upon by policy makers in enhancing energy efficiency in buildings and mitigating against climate change. This has been implemented by embarking on retrofitting improvement programs in building projects. Furthermore, the authors agree that one of the surest forms of compliance that has originated in Lagos Nigeria is the process of improvements in their building permitting licenses for newer buildings to ensure compliance with energy efficiency standards thereby improving sustainability.

In another study by (Afolabi and Adedire 2023) on adaptive strategies used in achieving thermal comfort within buildings, the authors have identified 52 strategies which they grouped into urban design (vegetation), effective building design (right choice of building materials), insulation (low thermal mass of building envelopes) and occupants indoor behaviors (reduction of energy consumption) as effective ways of achieving these. They further categorized these different strategies according to their different applications at the various stages of the building process to include predesign, design, construction and post construction. While also finding lasting solutions to indoor thermal comfort of building occupants, (Bashir and Leite 2024) have suggested the use of aerogel as insulation materials within buildings but due to their associated high costs, they recommend further research in this innovative application. Other innovative methods as highlighted by (Oginni 2024) on the use of vegetation in selected school buildings in Lagos which the study confirmed that the overall amount of green spaces within had a direct impact on the outside temperature and indoor comfort of the building occupants thereby making the classroom more resilient in the face of climate change. It is also important to note that the use of locally sourced materials like timber, bamboo, earths based construction and thatch all aid in enhancing thermal comfort within the building spaces in Southeastern Nigeria (Egbum, Anaebo, David and Barnaby 2023). In addition, it has generally been suggested in Nigeria that there should be improved awareness about sustainable buildings which have a very important role to play in climate change adaptation and mitigation of buildings in the Nigerian built environment (Akah, Olurotimi and Yetunde 2023).

4.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study's focus was on identifying energy efficiency strategies that could improve indoor thermal comfort of building occupants while also enhancing reduced energy consumption patterns in buildings in

the face of climate change challenges being faced in the built environment in Nigeria. The study involved an in-depth content analysis and literature review and generated information and new knowledge about the present state and future trends about energy efficiency and buildings occupants' wellbeing in the study area. It is evident that knowledge gained from this study offers a strong foundation on the studies area of focus regarding energy efficiency and buildings thermal comfort indoor adaptation techniques towards resilient buildings operations in Nigeria. The study also conducted a comprehensive literature review of 46 articles related to the studies area of concentration highlighting the importance of energy efficiency in buildings, improving occupant's indoor comfort and enhancement of energy consumption within. The key findings are presented below:

- Existing buildings can be retrofitted towards making them more energy efficient thereby increasing their values while also enhancing their environmental impacts on the built environment. These can be in the form of applications of energy efficient envelope systems applications both internally and externally, high efficiency window systems and smart thermostats. Future studies should place more emphasis on effective building envelope systems in buildings in Nigeria.
- The effects of climate change on buildings can be effectively reduced by the adoption of climate friendly technologies while building. Secondly, two major mitigation and adaptation strategies against the effects of climate change that can also be adopted are planting of trees and effective greening of the buildings environment.
- In addition, 52 adaptive strategies used in achieving thermal comfort within buildings were identified and grouped into urban design (vegetation), effective building design (right choice of building materials), insulation (low thermal mass of building envelopes) and occupants indoor behaviors (reduction of energy consumption) as effective ways of achieving these.
- It is also important to note that the use of locally sourced materials like timber, bamboo, earths based construction and thatch all aid in enhancing thermal comfort within the building spaces in Southeastern Nigeria.
- In addressing thermal comfort of building occupants, it has been suggested that there are two models directly associated with knowledge relating to thermal comfort which are the heat balance theory and the adaptive model. The adaptive model refers to the ability of building occupants to adapt to noticeable thermal changes inherent within the environment domiciled while also enhancing their comfort.
- The study revealed a significant knowledge gap in the implementation of smart building technologies and automated systems for energy management in Nigerian buildings, indicating a need for greater technological integration in building management systems.
- The research highlighted the critical role of policy frameworks and building codes in promoting energy-efficient building practices, though enforcement remains a significant challenge in the Nigerian context

While the present study highlights the importance of energy efficiency, buildings thermal comfort indoor adaptation techniques towards resilient buildings operations in Nigeria, by retrofitting existing buildings and integrating energy efficiency measure in the design and construction of buildings, it is believed that in the long run, these will all be effective in combating the effects of climate change on buildings in Nigeria. Further studies need to be conducted especially in the areas surrounding the effects of climate change on buildings in Nigeria due to the limited literature that exist in this global challenge facing the world. It is suggested that based on the Nigerian context, future studies that place emphasis on newer technological advances on adaptation and mitigating strategies in buildings should be carried out which include smart technologies and energy efficient temperature control devices. More attention should also be placed on effectively generating data that enables estimation of actual buildings energy usage and consumption patterns in order to address energy efficiency issues in buildings which have continued to be limitations in effective assessment. Development of comprehensive building energy codes specific to different climatic zones in Nigeria. Also, the implementation of mandatory energy performance certificates for new

buildings and creation of incentive programs for building owners who implement energy-efficient retrofits. Training programs for architects, engineers, and construction professionals on energy-efficient building practices, Public awareness campaigns about the benefits of energy-efficient buildings, Development of specialized courses in universities focusing on sustainable building design.

The successful implementation of these recommendations will require sustained commitment from all stakeholders, including government agencies, building professionals, academic institutions, and the private sector. Regular monitoring and evaluation of progress will be essential to ensure the effectiveness of these measures in achieving the desired outcomes of improved building energy efficiency and enhanced occupant comfort in Nigeria.

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